

DAMAGE DETECTION OF CFRP LAMINATED BY USING LOCALIZED FLEXIBILITY METHOD

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SUMMARY: This paper presents modal-based structural damage detection. Specifically, we focus on localized flexibility properties that can be deduced from the experimentally determined global flexibility matrix. We describe the underlying damage detection theory that can be viewed a generalized flexibility formulation in three different generalized coordinates, viz., localized or substructural displacement, elemental deformation-basis and element strain-basis. The three localized flexibilities are applied to a CFRP beam having interior damage. The results show that the elemental strain-basis flexibility is most accurate in detecting the damage of the CFRP laminates.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, Damage Detection, Localized Flexibility, Substructural Flexibility, Deformation-based Flexibility, Strain-based Flexibility, Inverse Problem, FEM

INTRODUCTION

CFRP laminated composites have very favorable strength and stiffness-to-weight ratio among engineering materials, which make their aerospace applications highly desirable as weight savings translate directly into higher performance. A major concern in using these composites is their vulnerability to impulsive loading by space debris, pebbles and dusts. This is because crack or damage caused by inter-laminar delaminations or fiber-matrix debonding in the laminated composites, although not visible on the surface, significantly reduces their strength and/or stiffness. A rational method for the detection of damage location and damage modes or mechanisms in composites can therefore facilitate a wider acceptance of composites by the practicing engineers.

To this end, several damage detection methods have been proposed, which include ultrasonic crack detection, wave propagation and scattering, modal testing, among other [1],[2]. The objective of the present paper is to offer a model-based damage detection technique by relying on vibrations test data. It should be mentioned that on-site vibration test is becoming economical and mobile as new miniaturized sensors of both contact and non-contact high-fidelity types which are readily available. In addition, a significant body of research in structural dynamics system identification has enabled to obtain a large order of structural models from test data. This in turn

has provided an impetus for updating the finite element models of structures to reconcile with system-identified models.

Early model updating approaches have involved the modification of assembled stiffness and mass matrices to correlate to the available modes and mode shapes identified from test. As this task must choose a particular solution from an infinite number of possible solutions, a least-square solution that minimizes the norm of the adjusted matrix has been frequently employed. Recent modifications to this general approach involve minimizing the rank of the matrix update [3]. This method is efficient and have been used successfully for both model adjustments and structural damage detection. Further enhancements include sensitivity-based element-by-element method [4] and its efficient computer implementation algorithm [5]. We note that, as an alternative to the preceding approaches, a hierarchical neural network approach has been successfully adopted to an inverse analysis of the damage detection [6] and the identification of boundary conditions of the CFRP laminates[7]. It should be noted that detection of damage based on these approaches rely on the changes in global stiffness properties.

A distinct alternative to the global stiffness approaches is a theory for localized flexibilities which is designed to handle the elemental or substructural deformations or strains as the final system-identified information [8],[9],[10]. The theoretical basis of this approach is given in the variational formulations of partitioned structural system [11],[12]. It should be noted that applications of the localized damage identification techniques [8] to experimental data have been limited to discrete joint cracks in beams and bridge damages. The objective of the present paper is to extend their applications to continuum composites.

The present paper is organized as follows. First, a brief review of the variational formulation of the partitioned equations of motion for a vibrating structures is described. Second, by solving for the partitioned or substructural displacement, the relation between the partitioned flexibility and the global flexibility is established. The relation of the global frequency response function (FRF) to the partitioned FRF is then established by using the input/output invariance requirement. Third, by decomposing the elemental output displacement vector in terms of the strain amplitudes, a theory for strain output-based damage detection is derived by treating the strain gauge records. The damage location is estimated by the present three localized flexibility changes for CFRP laminated beam [13]. The numerical predictions are compared with the experimental results, which indicates that the localized flexibility changes yield both accurate identification of damage location and the damage levels.

REVIEW OF LOCALIZED FLEXIBILITY FORMULATION

In what follows is a summary of the partitioned formulation of the discrete structural system [8], the derivation of localized flexibility matrix in term of the global flexibility and the partitioned interface topology [11],[12], and the basis transformations of the localized flexibility matrices into the deformation and strain-basis flexibilities [8],[10].

Global Flexibility Matrix

The discrete energy functional Π for a linear damped structure can be expressed as

$$\Pi(\mathbf{u}_g) = \mathbf{u}_g^T \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{K}_g \mathbf{u}_g - \mathbf{f}_g^D \right),$$

$$\mathbf{K}_g = \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{L}, \quad \mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}^1 & & \\ & \mathbf{K}^2 & \\ & & \mathbf{K}^{n_s} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f}_g^D = \mathbf{f}_g - \mathbf{M}_g \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g - \mathbf{C}_g \dot{\mathbf{u}}_g \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u}_g is the displacement vector of the assembled structure; \mathbf{f}_g^D is D`Alambert`s force vector that consists of the applied force vector \mathbf{f}_g , the resisting inertia force $\mathbf{M}_g \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g$, and the dissipating force $\mathbf{C}_g \dot{\mathbf{u}}_g$; \mathbf{K}_g is the assembled stiffness matrix; \mathbf{C}_g is the assembled damping matrix; \mathbf{M}_g is the mass matrix of the assembled structure; \mathbf{K} is the block diagonal collection of unassembled substructural stiffness matrices \mathbf{K}^S ; \mathbf{L} is the Boolean assembly matrix that relates the global and substructural displacements; the superscript (\cdot) designates time differentiation, and the subscript (g) designates ‘an assembled global structure’ to distinguish from ‘partitioned substructures’. The discrete damped, time-invariant linear equations of motion for vibrating structures can be obtained from the stationary value of the preceding discrete energy functional, viz., $\delta\Pi = 0$:

$$\mathbf{M}_g \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g + \mathbf{C}_g \dot{\mathbf{u}}_g + \mathbf{K}_g \mathbf{u}_g = \mathbf{f}_g \quad (2)$$

The input-output relation, referred to as the *frequency response function* (FRF), is obtained by substituting a harmonic form of the input-output vectors as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_g \\ \mathbf{f}_g \end{bmatrix} = e^{j\omega t} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{u}}_g \\ \bar{\mathbf{f}}_g \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

and solving for the frequency-domain output $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_g$:

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}}_g = \mathbf{H}_g(\omega) \bar{\mathbf{f}}_g, \quad \mathbf{H}_g(\omega) = (\mathbf{K}_g + j\omega \mathbf{C}_g - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}_g)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_g(\omega)$ will be called the ‘global’ flexibility matrix and becomes to \mathbf{K}_g^{-1} ($=\mathbf{F}_g$) in the quasi-static limit ($\omega \rightarrow 0$). This matrix can be obtained in terms of the eigen modes Φ and eigen values Λ as

$$\mathbf{F}_g = \Phi \Lambda^{-1} \Phi^T, \quad \Phi^T \mathbf{M}_g \Phi = \mathbf{I}, \quad \Phi^T \mathbf{K}_g \Phi = \Lambda \quad (5)$$

In practice, the size of the experimentally identified global flexibility matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_g = \Phi_m \Lambda_m^{-1} \Phi_m^T \quad (6)$$

where the subscript m denotes the measured modes and mode shapes which are substantially smaller than the analytical mode size.

Substructural Flexibility Equation

Since our objective is to identify the damage location and the global flexibility-based damage indicators are known to mask localized damage attributes, we employ a general partitioned flexibility method presented by Park and Felippa [6] to relate the experimentally measured global flexibility matrix in Eq.(5) in term of the corresponding localized flexibility matrices. This is accomplished as follows. First, a structure that is in equilibrium under applied forces is partitioned into substructures or elements. Hence, each of the substructures formed after partitioning would be subject to the corresponding applied forces plus the Lagrange multipliers acting along the substructural partition interfaces. In order to maintain the kinematical compatibility along the partitioned boundaries, the displacement vector of the partitioned substructures \mathbf{u} must satisfy the following relation:

$$\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}_g = 0 \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{u} are the collections of all the substructural displacements, and \mathbf{L} is the compatibility Boolean operator that is introduced in assembling the global stiffness matrix from the block diagonal substructural stiffness matrices given in Eq.(1). The element-by-element force vector \mathbf{f} that is conjugate with the substructural displacement is given by

$$\mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}_g \quad (8)$$

so that the desired FRF must assume the following form:

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{H}(\omega) \bar{\mathbf{f}} \quad (9)$$

Observe that Eq.(9) relates the input $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ that is acting on each substructure defined in Eq.(8) to the output of individual substructural displacements $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ introduced in Eq.(7). Therefore, by introducing a Lagrange multiplier vector λ_ℓ to enforce the kinematic compatibility condition Eq.(7), the system energy functional expressed in terms of the global nodal variables given in Eq.(1) is transformed into the three-variable functional:

$$\Pi(\mathbf{u}, \lambda_\ell, \mathbf{u}_g) = \mathbf{u}^T \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} \right) - \lambda_\ell^T \mathbf{B}^T (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}_g) \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{C} are the substructural mass and damping matrices, and \mathbf{B} is a constraint projection matrix that extracts the partition boundary substructural nodes. The stationary value of the above functional leads to the following equations of motion for partitioned structures:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{M}} + \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \mathbf{K} & -\mathbf{B} & 0 \\ -\mathbf{B}^T & 0 & \mathbf{L}_b \\ 0 & \mathbf{L}_b^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \lambda_\ell \\ \mathbf{u}_g \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_b = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{L} \quad (11)$$

The substructure-by-substructure FRF that is sought after can now be obtained from Eq.(11) as

$$\mathbf{H}(\omega) = \mathbf{H}_e(\omega) \{ \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}_B(\omega) [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{L}_b \mathbf{H}_L(\omega) \mathbf{L}_b^T \mathbf{K}_B(\omega)] \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{H}_e(\omega) \} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_e(\omega) = (\mathbf{K} + j\omega\mathbf{C} - \omega^2\mathbf{M})^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{K}_B(\omega) = (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{H}_e(\omega) \mathbf{B})^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{H}_L(\omega) = (\mathbf{L}_b^T \mathbf{K}_B(\omega) \mathbf{L}_b)^{-1}$$

It can be shown that the substructural FRF $\mathbf{H}(\omega)$ can also be obtained in terms of the global FRF $\mathbf{H}_g(\omega)$, viz.,

$$\mathbf{H}(\omega) = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{H}_g(\omega) \mathbf{L}^T = \mathbf{L} (\mathbf{K}_g + j\omega\mathbf{C}_g - \omega^2\mathbf{M}_g)^{-1} \mathbf{L}^T \quad (13)$$

Observe that the substructural FRF given by Eq.(12) reveals the substructural compositions consisting of the substructural mass, damping and stiffness matrices. On the other hand, the same FRF obtained by the input/output invariance property given by Eq.(13) masks the substructural compositions, showing only the global quantities. It is their combined use that leads to an important application in detecting damages as shown below. For the quasistatic limit, i.e., ($\omega \rightarrow 0$), the two expressions provide the following Ricatti-like equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{L}\mathbf{F}_g\mathbf{L}^T &= \mathbf{F} \{ \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{F}_B^{-1} [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{L}_b\mathbf{F}_L\mathbf{L}_b^T\mathbf{F}_B^{-1}] \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{F} \} \\ \mathbf{F} &= \mathbf{K}^{-1}, \mathbf{F}_B = (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{F} \mathbf{B}), \mathbf{F}_L = (\mathbf{L}_b^T \mathbf{F}_B^{-1} \mathbf{L}_b)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where F is called the substructural flexibility matrix of block diagonal form. Eq.(14) has been used by Alvin and Park [9] for detecting the substructural flexibility via an iterative solution procedure. This will be further assessed in the applications section.

Deformation-Basis Flexibilities

The substructural flexibility matrix $F=K^{-1}$ given in Eq.(14) consists of both free-free deformation modes plus the rigid body modes. This poses no difficulty when the experimentally identified global flexibility F_g in Eq.(6) is a full basis matrix, viz., the eigenvector Φ_m is a square matrix. In practice the identified modes are often a fraction of the sensor output numbers, namely, for Φ_m ($s \gg m$) where s is the number of the sensors and m is the identified mode numbers. This observation motivated us to transform the free-free substructural flexibility matrix F into a constrained deformation flexibility which can lead to a sharper indication of damage. Let us decompose the substructural displacements u further into deformational and rigid parts:

$$u = d + R\alpha \quad (15)$$

where d is the deformational part, R describe the substructural rigid-mode shapes, and α are the rigid-mode amplitudes. In order to eliminate the rigid-body motions from the substructural displacements, we partition Eq.(15) according to:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_c \\ u_f \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} d_c \\ d_f \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} R_c \\ R_f \end{Bmatrix} \alpha, \quad R = \begin{bmatrix} R^1 & & & \\ & R^2 & & \\ & & \cdot & \\ & & & R^{n_s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where R_c is a square invertible submatrix corresponding to ‘temporarily constrained nodes’ and R_f refers to unconstrained nodes. Hence, R_c would be a (3 x 3) matrix. Similarly, the constrained-node rigid-body amplitudes R_c for other substructural cases can be chosen. Solving for α from the first row of Eq.(16), we obtain

$$\alpha = R_c^{-1}(u_c - d_c) \quad (17)$$

We now introduce a deformation measure that represents deformations at nodes f with respect to nodes c :

$$v = d_f - R_f R_c^{-1} d_c = Tu = TLu_g, \quad T = [-\bar{R} \quad I], \quad \bar{R} = R_f R_c^{-1} \quad (18)$$

Using this relation, plus its conjugate force vectors given by

$$T^T f_v = f \Rightarrow L^T T^T f_v = L^T f = f_g \quad (19)$$

The variational functional Eq.(10) expressed in terms of the substructural displacement u is transformed into that of the deformation variable v , which in the quasi-static limit becomes:

$$\Pi(v, \lambda_v, u_g) = v^T (\frac{1}{2} K_v v - f_v) - \lambda_v^T B_v^T (v - TLu_g), \quad K = T^T K_v T \quad (20)$$

A simple expression is obtained if the constraint operator B_v is chosen as a nullspace of TL , viz.,

$$B_v^T (TL) = 0 \quad (21)$$

So that the stationary condition $\delta\Pi = 0$ of Eq.(20) yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_v & -B_v \\ -B_v^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} v \\ \lambda_v \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_v \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

which will be called the deformational quasi-static equations of motion for partitioned structures. A Riccati-like equation which relates the global flexibility to the deformation-basis substructural flexibility can be obtained in a similar manner as for the substructural displacement case Eq.(14):

$$TLF_g L^T T^T = P_v^T F_v P_v, \quad F_v = K_v^{-1}, \quad P_v = I - B_v [B_v^T F_v B_v]^{-1} B_v^T F_v \quad (23)$$

Strain-Basis Flexibilities

We have experienced that the use of the deformational flexibilities F_v yields an adequate identification of damage locations. In many applications not only identifying damage locations but also damage mechanisms are equally important. For only through understanding damage mechanisms one can develop damage prevention measures. An effective approach to detect damage mechanisms is to utilize strain-basis substructural flexibilities. As an example, a typical substructure consists of membrane, transverse shear and bending strains. By identifying which of the three strains underwent a major strain change, one may deduce the damage mechanisms. The necessary transformation to obtain a strain-basis flexibilities is shown below. Let us assume that the strain output s can be related to the substructural displacement u according to

$$s = Du = D L u_g \quad (24)$$

where D is the discrete strain-displacement relation matrix that can be derived in a variety of ways, e.g., by relying on the finite element shape functions. With this change of basis, one arrives at the following strain-basis functional and the corresponding equations of motion in quasi-static form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi(s, \lambda_s) &= s^T \left(\frac{1}{2} K_s s - f_s \right) - \lambda_s^T B_s^T (s - D L u_g), \quad K = D^T K_s D, \quad B_s^T (D L) = 0 \\ L^T D^T f_s = f_g &\Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} K_s & -B_s \\ -B_s^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} s \\ \lambda_s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_s \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The global flexibility F_g is then related to the strain-basis substructural flexibility F_s according to:

$$DLF_g L^T D^T = P_s^T F_s P_s, \quad F_s = K_s^{-1}, \quad P_s = I - B_s [B_s^T F_s B_s]^{-1} B_s^T F_s \quad (26)$$

which can be used not only for localized damage detection but more importantly for identifying damage mechanisms.

APPLICATIONS TO DAMAGE DETECTION IN CONTINUUM CFRP COMPOSITES

To illustrate the applicability of the localized damage detection techniques reviewed in the preceding section to continuum composites, we first evaluate the methods to analytical problems. Validation of the methods to experimental data is then followed.

Fig.1: Partitioned Elements and the Location of the Strain Gage

Analytical Demonstration

In order to demonstrate the validity of the damage detection methods outlined in the preceding section, a CFRP [0/45/90/-45]_{2S} quasi-isotropic laminated beam having width of 15mm, length of 180mm and 2mm thickness and fixed at both ends is chosen as an example (see Fig.1). The beam is divided into 9 same-size plate elements in the FEM analysis and the bending rigidity of the center(5th) element is assumed to 85% value of other elements due to the damage. For offering the relative performance of three methods, the global flexibility F_g is adopted as an inverse of the global stiffness matrix that is obtained from the corresponding FEM analysis. A homotopy iterative procedure [14] is then used to obtain the free-free substructural flexibility F given in Eq.(14), the deformation-basis flexibility F_v in Eq.(23) and the strain-basis flexibility F_s in Eq.(26). When the strain-basis flexibilities are to be obtained, the homotopy iteration procedure involves

$$\begin{aligned} F_s^{k+1} &= F_s^k + \beta E(r_s^{k+1}) \\ r_s^{k+1} &= DL F_g L^T D^T - P_s^{kT} F_s^k P_s^k \\ P_s &= I - B_s [B_s^T F_s B_s]^{-1} B_s^T F_s \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where β is an iteration parameter and E extracts the non-zero attributes of the assumed strain-basis flexibilities from r_s . In order to choose a desirable parameter β that maximizes the homotopy iteration efficiency, a numerical experiment has been carried out. Fig.2 shows the number of iterations vs. the parameter β , from which $\beta=5.24$ is adopted for the present example problem. For damage detection we have employed the following damage indicator D :

$$D_j = \text{diag} (F_j^D - F_j^H) / F_j^H \quad (28)$$

where the superscripts D and H refer to damaged and healthy substructure, and the subscript j designates the substructural component or degree of freedom.

When the free-free substructural flexibility method is used, the damage is detected at the degree of freedom from 15 to 18 corresponding to 5th element as shown in Fig.3. The resulting damage indicator provides the location of damage correctly and the rigidity ratio of the corresponding element shows the assumed value

Fig.2: Effect of Homotopy Iteration Parameter on Iteration

Fig.3: Damage Detection Based on Substructural Flexibility

Fig.4: Damage Detection Based on Deformation Flexibility

Fig.5: Damage Detection Based on Strain Flexibility

of 0.85. As for the deformation-based flexibility method, the damage should occur at the degree of freedoms 9 and 10. Fig.4 shows that the damage indicator correctly traces those two degrees of freedom and that the rigidity ratio is the assumed reduced rigidity. Finally, Fig.5 shows the damage indication based on the strain-basis flexibilities not only correctly detects the damaged 5th element but also computes correctly the rigidity ratio of 85%.

Fig.6 shows the comparison of three method to the same problem illustrated in Fig.3,4 and 5 by using only the first three eigen values and eigen vectors in the global flexibility matrix F_g . Since the only the first three eigenvalues and modes are used for calculating the global flexibility F_g in Eq.(6), each rigidity ratio cannot be accurately computed. Nevertheless, the locations of damaged elements are correctly determined as shown in Fig.6. As far as the damage rigidity ratio is concerned, both the deformation-basis and the strain-basis damage indication can predict it well within acceptable accuracy ranges and the strain-basis is better than the deformed-basis.

Next, the effects of the additional damage locations for the same CFRP laminated beam are investigated by varying the rigidity in the 2nd, 3rd and 5th elements via the strain based flexibility method. For this example problem, the bending rigidity EI is reduced by 85% for those elements by modifying the first three eigenvalues and eigenvectors in the global flexibility matrix F_g accordingly. Fig.7 shows that the bending rigidity of the damaged elements are different somewhat for all three cases but their locations are correctly determined.

Application to Experimental Data

We have carried out the damage detection procedure to experimental strain data obtained on the CFRP quasi-isotropic laminated beam as mentioned above. The strain data have been measured at the center of the nine elements on the beam specimens as shown in Fig.1. Three beams have been tested with their 85% bending rigidities ratio on element 2, element 3 and element 5, and 46% bending rigidity ratio on element 5, respectively. These bending rigidity reductions have been realized by varying the stacking sequences of fourth or surface layer at the damaged element locations as shown in Fig.8. The beam have been then subjected to modal tests with impact hammer excitations which closely effect impulse forces. The frequency response functions (FRFs) have been obtained using a single input and multi-output (SIMO) analyzer and

Fig.6: Damage Detection By Using First Three Vibration Mode

Fig.7: Analytical Damage Detection Based on Strain Flexibility for Various Damage Locations

Fig.8: Fiber Orientation for the Experimental Specimens

the strains are measured for the first three eigenmodes. Fig.9 shows the first three eigenmodes for the CFRP laminated test beams. Note that the mode shape differences between the nominal and damaged specimen are most pronounced at damaged element 5 location for the first and 3rd modes. Using the experimentally determined three global flexibility modes, damage indicators based on the strain-basis flexibility changes are computed and shown in Fig.10. By comparing the experimental cases shown in Fig.10 with the analytical cases (see Fig.7), it is seen that the damage locations are correctly determined. The bending rigidities of the damaged elements are overestimated somewhat for all four test cases including the lower ratio of 46 % case but well within acceptable accuracy ranges.

Fig.9: First Three Vibration Mode for the Flawless Specimen and the Imperfect Ones

Fig.10: Experimental Damage Detection Based on Strain Flexibility for Various Damage Locations and Bending Rigidity Ratios

CONCLUSION

The damage indicator that utilizes the three localized flexibilities has been applied to the damage detection of CFRP laminate composite beam. The free-free localized flexibility and the deformation-basis flexibilities can make use of conventional output data such as acceleration or displacement. The strain-basis localized flexibility can utilize a combination of the conventional modal testy output as well as the strain output. The damage in the CFRP beams have been realized by varying the stacking sequence of layers covering specific elements. The main features of the present study are summarized as follows.

1) The relative accuracy fidelities of the three localized flexibilities are evaluated as applied to the damage detection of CFRP quasi-isotropic laminated beams analytically. All three flexibility methods accurately captured the locations of rigidity changes. Among the three, the strain-basis flexibility method is most accurate.

2) In using experimentally determined three-mode global flexibility matrices of the four test composite beams, damage detections are carried out by the strain-basis flexibility method. The results demonstrate that damage locations are identified with high confidence as well as reasonably accurate change in the bending rigidities.

3) From the computational viewpoint, the homotopy parameter choice can influence the data analysis efficiency greatly. Further studies are needed to tune the parameter ranges so that large-order problems can become computationally feasible.

It should be noted that the present damage location and damage mechanisms identification procedure based on the localized strain-basis flexibilities can process each substructural input/output independently for spatially localized damage assessment, thus making the present procedure attractive for online health monitoring. This and related aspects are under active investigation.

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